

Solvent Transport and Ion-Solvation of some Copper(II) Salts in Methanol—Dimethylsulphoxide Mixtures

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The solvent transport numbers and the standard Gibbs free energies of transfer of copper(II) acetate, benzoate and iodate have been determined in methanol—DMSO mixtures over the complete range of solvent compositions at 30° by EMF and solubility measurements. The solvent transport number Δ passes through a maximum of 1.2 and 1.4 at $X_{\text{DMSO}}=0.55$ for copper(II) acetate and benzoate respectively, while for iodate, $\Delta_{\text{max}}=1.2$ at $X_{\text{DMSO}}=0.45$. The solubilities of these salts increase monotonically with the increase in DMSO content of the medium. The standard Gibbs free energies of transfer from methanol to methanol—DMSO mixtures were calculated from the thermodynamic solubility products of the salts in these mixtures. The ionic free energies of transfer of Cu^{2+} and the anions were computed on the basis of the negligible liquid junction potential method. It was concluded that all the salts are heteroselectively solvated in these mixtures on the basis of these measurements.

THE solvation behaviour of electrolytes in mixed solvents has been the subject of considerable attention^{1,2} in recent years. This is because of the observation that the selective sorting out of the components of a binary mixed solvent by the ions of the electrolyte has potential technological applications^{3,4}.

In earlier investigations from our laboratory^{5,6}, the selective solvation of a number of silver(I) salts has been studied in a number of protic+dipolar aprotic solvent mixtures employing Gibbs energies of solvation and solvent transport number measurements. These studies have been recently extended to copper(II) salts in water—DMSO mixtures⁷ which are known to possess strong solvent-solvent interactions leading to different types of selective solvation behaviour at low and high molefractions of DMSO in the case of silver(I) salts. In continuation of the above work, we report here the results on the preferential solvation of copper(II) salts in the related methanol—DMSO mixtures using the above mentioned experimental approaches. This mixed solvent is of particular interest because DMSO is very well-known as a solvent of high (DN=29.8) which can solvate cations more strongly than methanol.

Experimental

DMSO (B.D.H., L.R.) was purified by known method⁸. The middle fraction boiling at 60° under a pressure of 12 mm/Hg was collected and stored out of contact with air under molecular sieves (5Å). Methanol (B.D.H., G.R.) was first dehydrated by refluxing with lime and subsequently with magnesium turnings and iodine. At each stage, the constant-boiling middle fraction was collected and finally stored under molecular sieves

(4Å)⁹. Anhydrous copper(II) benzoate was prepared¹⁰ according to the reported method¹⁰. The salt was first dried in air, then over anhydrous CaCl_2 under reduced pressure and finally over P_2O_5 at 110–120° under reduced pressure for over 2 days to yield the anhydrous compound. Copper(II) iodate was prepared by double decomposition of copper(II) nitrate and potassium iodate in aqueous solution¹¹. The anhydrous salt was prepared from this sample by heating upto 240° and was stored over anhydrous CaCl_2 under reduced pressure. Thermogravimetric analysis confirmed the anhydrous nature of the prepared copper(II) benzoate and iodate. Copper(II) acetate monohydrate (Merck, L.R.) was twice recrystallised from conductivity water. A few drops of 2*N* acetic acid was added during dissolution of the salt to prevent hydrolysis. Copper(II) perchlorate was prepared as reported earlier¹². The purity of all the salts was checked by estimating their copper content spectrophotometrically. Copper(II) acetate was used in its monohydrate form in all the experiments. Silver(I) perchlorate was prepared according to the reported procedure¹³. Silver electrodes were prepared following the known procedure¹⁴ and copper electrodes were obtained by electrolytically depositing copper on to platinum spiral electrodes (wire dia. =0.5 mm) sealed in glass tubes according to the reported method¹⁵. Only freshly prepared electrodes, whose bias potentials were less than 0.5 mV, were used in all EMF measurements. A U-shaped cell fitted with ground joints at the top and a G_3 frit in the middle, to reduce the inter-diffusion of the electrolyte from the half-cells, was employed in solvent transport number measurements. A Keithley solid state electrometer (model 602), having an input impedance greater than $10^{14} \Omega$ was used in EMF measurements. The dielectric constant of the solvent mixtures was determined

with a D_x meter 60GK (Fransz Kustner Nachf KG, Dresden). All measurements were carried out at 30±0.1°.

Determination of solvent transport number (Δ): A concentration cell (A) with transference, proposed by Wagner¹⁶, was used for determining the solvent transport number (Δ) for all the salts in these solvent mixtures.

where, X⁻ = CH₃COO⁻, C₆H₅COO⁻ or IO₃⁻; A = DMSO; M = methanol.

In this cell, the two half-cells contain saturated solutions of the salt in solvent mixtures differing slightly in solvent composition (i.e. X''_A - X'_A = 0.1, maintained throughout). The EMF of cell (A) is given by the relation,

$$E = \frac{-RT}{2F} \frac{(X''_A - X'_A)}{X_A(1 - X_A)} \Delta \left(1 + \frac{d \ln f_A}{d \ln X_A} \right) \quad (1)$$

where the various terms have their usual significance. The term (d ln f_A/d ln X_A) accounts for the variation of the activity coefficient of DMSO with mole fraction in these mixtures. It was evaluated from the vapour pressure data of these mixtures reported elsewhere¹⁷. X_A is the average mole fraction of DMSO between the two half-cells and is equal to (X''_A + X'_A)/2. Δ may be defined as the net increase in the number of moles of DMSO in the cathode compartment, with the mean molar velocity of solvent mixture as reference, when one Faraday of electricity is passed through the cell (A) containing the salt at given solvent composition. The results are given in Table 1 and are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Variation of Δ° with X_{DMSO} in methanol-DMSO; copper(II) (○), acetate, (●) benzoate and (△) iodate; Temp. = 30°.

Solubility measurements: The details of preparation of the saturated solutions of the salts in methanol-DMSO mixtures have been described earlier¹⁸. The clear saturated solution, after separating from the excess solid, was acidified with 4N H₂SO₄ (4-5 ml) and the copper was displaced with zinc powder. The separated copper was dissolved in concentrated HNO₃ and the excess acid was destroyed by boiling with urea. The solution was then evaporated to a small volume, cooled and made upto the mark in a standard flask of desired volume. To an aliquot of this solution, liquor NH₃ was added and made upto the desired volume and the absorbance measured at the λ_{max} of cuprammine complex, i.e. 620 nm. The solubilities and the solubility products are given in Table 2.

Determination of ΔG_i° (salt): The standard Gibbs energies of transfer of the salts from methanol to methanol-DMSO mixtures were computed using the relation,

$$\Delta G_i^\circ (\text{salt}) = -RT \ln \frac{K_{sp}^{(S)}}{K_{sp}^{(M)}} \quad (2)$$

where S is methanol-DMSO mixture of a given composition, M is methanol, and K_{sp} is the thermodynamic solubility product of the salt, and is given by

$$K_{sp} = 4S^2 \gamma_{\pm}^2 \quad (3)$$

where, γ_± is the mean molal activity coefficient of the salt which in turn has been calculated from the extended Debye-Hückel equation,

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{AZ_+Z_- \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + aB \sqrt{\mu}} \quad (4)$$

where, A and B are the Debye-Hückel constants, μ the ionic strength of the solution and a the ion-size parameter calculated from the work of Kielland¹⁹. The a values used for copper acetate and iodate are 10.5 Å and for copper benzoate is 12 Å. The calculated values of ΔG_i° (salt) are given in Table 3.

Determination of ΔG_i° (Cu²⁺): The standard Gibbs energies of transfer of copper(II) ion, ΔG_i° (Cu²⁺), from methanol to methanol-DMSO mixtures, were determined by the negligible liquid junction potential (nljp) method, of Parker²⁰, using cell (B).

where, M is methanol, S is methanol-DMSO mixture and AN is acetonitrile. The ΔG_i° (Cu²⁺) value was calculated from the measured EMF of the cell (B) using the relation,

$$\Delta G_i^\circ (\text{Cu}^{2+}) = 2F(E_S - E_M) - RT \ln \frac{a_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}(\text{S})}{a_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}(\text{M})} \quad (5)$$

where, E_M and E_S are the EMFs of the cell (B) when the solvents in the right-hand half-cell are methanol and methanol-DMSO mixtures respec-

tively. The standard Gibbs transfer energies of the anions can be computed from the relation,

$$\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{CuX}_2) = \Delta G_i^\circ(\text{Cu}^{2+}) + 2\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{X}^-) \quad (6)$$

where, X⁻ is CH₃COO⁻, C₆H₅COO⁻ or IO₃⁻.

The transfer energies of Cu²⁺ and of anions so calculated are given in Table 3. The ΔG_i° data of the salt and the ions are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. ΔG_i° for copper(II) salts and the constituent ions in methanol-DMSO mixtures: (○) CH₃COO⁻, (◻) C₆H₅COO⁻, (●) IO₃⁻, (▲) Cu(CH₃COO)₂, (△) Cu(C₆H₅COO)₂, (▽) Cu(IO₃)₂ and (◻) Cu²⁺.

Results and Discussion

It is observed from Table 1 and Fig. 1 that the Δ values of DMSO for all the three copper(II) salts are positive and pass through maxima, viz. $\Delta_{\text{max}} = 1.2$ at $X_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.55$ for copper(II) acetate, $\Delta_{\text{max}} = 1.4$ at $X_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.55$ for copper(II) benzoate, and $\Delta_{\text{max}} = 1.2$ at $X_{\text{DMSO}} = 0.45$ for copper(II) iodate. Thus there is an enrichment of 1.2, 1.4 and 1.2 moles of DMSO in the cathode compartment per Faraday when saturated solutions of these salts are electrolysed at the solvent compositions mentioned above. It may be pointed that Δ depends upon ionic transport numbers and the four solvation numbers of cation and anion according to the equation,

$$\Delta = (X_M n_D^+ - X_D n_M^+) t_+ - (X_M n_D^- - X_D n_M^-) t_- \quad (7)$$

For a heteroselectively solvated electrolyte, n_D^+ and n_M^- are large while n_M^+ and n_D^- are small resulting in large Δ values. The transport of DMSO into the cathode compartment occurs largely through copper(II) ions while the anions transport methanol in the opposite direction. These two effects add together and therefore large positive Δ values ($\Delta > 1$) characterise heteroselective solvation of the salts in these solvent mixtures.

Variation of ΔG_i° of salt and ions: The free energies of transfer of the three copper(II) salts in methanol-DMSO mixtures are generally negative and decrease continuously with the addition of DMSO. This may be rationalised as follows. In a methanol-DMSO mixture, the acid strength of the methanol is reduced by its interactions with the

TABLE 1—EMF VALUES AND SOLVENT TRANSPORT NUMBERS OF DMSO FOR COPPER(II) SALTS IN METHANOL-DMSO MIXTURES AT 30°

X_{DMSO}	$(1 + \frac{d \ln f_{\text{DMSO}}}{d \ln X_{\text{DMSO}}})$	Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂		Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂		Cu(IO ₃) ₂	
		-E (mV)	Δ	-E (mV)	Δ	-E (mV)	Δ
0.05	0.05	37 ± 1	0.67 ± 0.03	44 ± 2	0.79 ± 0.04	—	—
0.15	1.199	30 ± 2	0.61 ± 0.04	39 ± 1	0.80 ± 0.03	14 ± 2	0.29 ± 0.04
0.25	1.611	32 ± 2	0.71 ± 0.04	33 ± 1	0.74 ± 0.03	40 ± 1	0.89 ± 0.03
0.35	1.677	33.5 ± 1	0.87 ± 0.03	30 ± 2	0.78 ± 0.04	49 ± 1	1.27 ± 0.03
0.45	1.708	22 ± 1	0.61 ± 0.03	25 ± 1	0.70 ± 0.03	43 ± 1	1.20 ± 0.03
0.55	1.623	42 ± 1	1.23 ± 0.03	49 ± 1	1.48 ± 0.03	27 ± 2	0.79 ± 0.04
0.65	1.495	29 ± 1	0.85 ± 0.03	21 ± 2	0.62 ± 0.04	18 ± 2	0.59 ± 0.04
0.75	1.328	30 ± 1	0.82 ± 0.03	19 ± 2	0.52 ± 0.04	16 ± 2	0.43 ± 0.04
0.85	1.618	35.5 ± 1	0.54 ± 0.03	20 ± 1	0.30 ± 0.03	8 ± 1	0.12 ± 0.03
0.95	0.400	23 ± 2	0.52 ± 0.04	17.5 ± 2	0.40 ± 0.04	15 ± 1	0.34 ± 0.03

TABLE 2—SOLUBILITIES (S) AND SOLUBILITY PRODUCTS OF COPPER(II) ACETATE, BENZOATE AND IODATE IN METHANOL-DMSO MIXTURES AT 30°

X_{DMSO}	D*	Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂		Cu(C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₂		Cu(IO ₃) ₂	
		S^{**} × 10 ³ mol kg ⁻¹	pK _{sp}	S^{**} × 10 ³ mol kg ⁻¹	pK _{sp}	S^{**} × 10 ⁴ mol kg ⁻¹	pK _{sp}
0.0	31.80	2.16	5.638	7.93	6.675	4.68	9.748
0.1	35.75	2.59	5.278	5.91	6.854	34.00	7.451
0.3	41.60	3.18	4.868	8.26	6.580	74.80	6.456
0.5	45.20	3.58	4.638	9.24	6.150	102.00	6.040
0.7	46.45	3.87	4.522	11.90	5.845	122.00	5.815
0.9	46.45	4.08	4.462	14.80	5.600	136.00	5.694
1.0	46.00	4.17	4.448	18.40	5.360	142.00	5.655

*Dielectric constant. **Precise to ±0.5%.

TABLE 3—STANDARD GIBBS TRANSFER ENERGY (kJ mol⁻¹) OF COPPER(II) SALTS* AND IONS* IN METHANOL—DMSO MIXTURES AT 30°

X_{DMSO}	$\text{Cu}(\text{OH},\text{COO})_2$	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO})_2$	$\text{Cu}(\text{IO}_3)_2$	ΔG_t°	Cu^{2+}	CH_3COO^-	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^-$	IO_3^-
0.1	-2.1	+1.1	-18.3		-4.3	-1.1	2.7	-4.5
0.3	-4.5	-0.56	-19.1		-20.0	7.7	9.7	0.45
0.5	-5.8	-3.1	-21.5		-35.3	14.7	16.1	6.7
0.7	-6.5	-4.8	-22.8		-45.0	18.3	20.1	11.1
0.9	-6.8	-6.3	-23.5		-52.2	22.7	23.0	14.4
1.0	-7.0	-7.6	-23.8		-57.5	25.3	25.0	16.8

*Transfer energies accurate to ± 0.2 kJ mol⁻¹.

very basic DMSO so that the methanol molecules now can only form a weaker bond with the copper(II) ions. The standard Gibbs energy of transfer of the copper(II) ion from methanol to methanol—DMSO mixtures is increasingly negative with increasing DMSO content of the medium indicating that the transfer of the copper(II) ion from methanol to methanol—DMSO mixtures is thermodynamically favoured. Thus a preferential solvation of copper(II) ion by DMSO in these mixtures is inferred. For low concentrations of DMSO where $X_{\text{DMSO}} < 0.1$, the Gibbs transfer energy of copper(II) ion is small. This suggests that in this range of DMSO concentrations, copper(II) ions retain the solvation shell containing largely methanol molecules. In the concentration range of $0.1 < X_{\text{DMSO}} < 0.5$, the slope of the plot of $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{Cu}^{2+})$ vs X_{DMSO} increases considerably. This increase may be attributed to the replacement of methanol molecules in the co-sphere of the copper(II) ion by DMSO molecules. At $X_{\text{DMSO}} > 0.5$, $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{Cu}^{2+})$ depends slightly on the solvent composition thus indicating that all the copper(II) ions are totally solvated by DMSO molecules. Observations of similar nature have recently been reported for copper(II) ions in H₂O—DMSO system²¹. The preferential solvation of copper(II) ions by DMSO may be attributed to the formation of specific complexes²² of the type $\text{Cu}(\text{DMSO})_n^{2+}$ whereby a $d_{\pi}-p_{\pi}$ charge transfer is made feasible. Also, the specific copper(II) ion—DMSO interactions may be considered as a case of hard-hard interactions coordinating via the oxygen atom of $>\text{S}=\text{O}$ group as DMSO is a hard solvent. Cations being Lewis type acceptors undergo hard-hard interactions with hard solvents like DMSO.

The standard Gibbs transfer energies of the anions viz. acetate, benzoate and iodate are increasingly positive with increasing DMSO content of the medium, thereby indicating a preferential solvation of the anions by methanol. The transfer energies of the anions (from methanol to methanol—DMSO mixtures) are in the order, $\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- \approx \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}^- > \text{IO}_3^-$, where the slightly higher values

for acetate ion may be attributed to the +I effect of the methyl group. In the case of benzoate ion, the -I effect of the phenyl group decreases the transfer free energy of this ion.

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References

- H. SCHNEIDER, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1976, **21**, 711.
- A. J. PARKER, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1981, **33**, 1437.
- O. POPOVICH and R. P. T. TOMKINS, "Non-aqueous Solution Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1981.
- S. JANARDHANAN and O. KALIDAS, *Rev Inorg Chem.*, 1984, **6**, 101.
- S. SUBRAMANIAN and O. KALIDAS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1984, **26**, 753.
- S. SUBRAMANIAN and O. KALIDAS, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 1987, **32**, 205.
- G. RAJENDRAN, T. K. SREE KUMAR and O. KALIDAS, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 1989, **46**, 249.
- D. L. MARICLE and W. G. HODGSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, **37**, 1562.
- J. K. GLADEN and C. FANNING, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 76.
- J. LEWIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 6464.
- M. O. SNEED, "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", Van Nostrand, 1954, Vol. II, p. 102
- A. LEWANDOWSKI, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1986, **31**, 59.
- G. RAJENDRAN and O. KALIDAS, *J. Chem Engg Data*, 1986, **31**, 226.
- W. J. OARMODY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **51**, 2901.
- R. L. BLOKHRA, Y. P. SRGHAL and V. K. KUTHIALA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1976, **21**, 1079.
- C. WAGNER in "Advances in Electrochemistry and Electrochemicals Engineering", eds. P. DELAHAY and C. W. TOBIAS, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1966, Vol. 4, p. 1.
- K. QUITZSCH, H. ULBRECHT and G. GRISLER, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **33**, 234.
- O. KALIDAS and H. SCHNEIDER, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **70**, 847.
- J. KELLAND, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1675
- A. J. PARKER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 1148.
- J. MALYSZKO and M. SCHNDO, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1988, **250**, 61.
- L. OHEMZY, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1984, **29**, 373.